

Reversed Phase Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Iron(III) on Silica Gel impregnated with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid and its Analytical Applications

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A rapid and selective method for the extraction of iron(III) with reversed phase extraction chromatographic technique on silica gel impregnated with high molecular weight carboxylic acid (SRS-100) has been reported. Quantitative extraction is achieved in the pH range 2.8–3.5 from acetic acid and sodium acetate solution. Effects of variables such as pH, eluting agents, and flow rate on extraction and elution have been studied. Exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger has been determined by the usual process. Iron(III) has been separated from several metal ions. In order to assess the possible analytical application, iron(III) has been separated from several multicomponent mixtures containing metal ions commonly associated with it. Attempts have been made to extract iron(III) from standard alloy and ore samples.

INDUSTRIAL effluents contain commonly associated elements along with iron. Therefore, it was considered worthwhile to explore an exchange chromatographic method for the separation of iron from its associated contaminants. High molecular weight carboxylic acid, SRS-100 acts as a cation-exchanger, the exchange properties being similar to those of organic cation exchange resins¹. In this paper, attempts have been made for the extractive separation of iron(III) by reversed phase extraction chromatography with SRS-100.

Experimental

A Elico LI-10 pH meter, a ECIL GS 5700A spectrophotometer and a chromatographic column (1.5 cm i.d.) of Borosil glass with a glass wool plug at the bottom were used.

The liquid cation-exchanger, SRS-100 (Shell Chemical, London) high molecular weight synthetic monocarboxylic acid ($C_{18} - C_{16}$) was used as such without any further purification². A stock solution of iron(III) (5.1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from ferric chloride (AnalaR) in deionised water and the solution was standardised by complexometric titration with EDTA using sulphosalicylic acid as the indicator³. Buffer solutions of desired pH were prepared from 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M sodium acetate solution in proper ratio. Lower pH values of the solution were adjusted with chloroacetic acid.

Preparation of ion-exchange material: Silica gel (30–120 mesh, B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapours of dimethyl dichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere⁴. Hydrophobic silica gel was coated by treating with SRS-100 in benzene. Evaporation was done in a rotary vacuum

evaporator. Excess organic reagent present in the exchanger was washed with 4 M HCl.

General extraction procedure: pH of the exchanger was maintained at 2.8 for all extractions. An aliquot of solution (containing 5.1 mg Fe^{III}) was sorbed on the column at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. The column was washed with buffer solution (pH=2.8; 20 ml). Iron(III) was eluted with different mineral acids and its amount in each fraction was determined complexometrically. The total operation time for each run was 1 h.

Results and Discussion

The extraction behaviour of iron(III) with SRS-100 was studied at different pH, keeping its concentration constant. The extraction of iron(III) increased with increasing pH and became quantitative at pH 2.8–3.5.

Eluting agents: It was observed that mineral acids are efficient eluents at concentrations above 0.5 M. HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃ and their salts and HClO₄ were tested as eluents. Elution of iron was quantitative with 1 M HCl and 0.5 M H₂SO₄. Salts of mineral acids such as NaCl, NaNO₃ and Na₂SO₄ were found to be poor eluting agents (Table 1). This might be due to the reason that replacement of iron with sodium is not favourable under this condition.

Exchange capacity: The exchange capacity of the cation-exchanger was determined by measuring the number of mg equiv. of sodium absorbed by 1 g of the dry exchanger in the hydrogen form. The exchanger was washed with 4 M HCl to remove organic impurity and the purified exchanger was dried in an evaporating dish. The exchanger (1 g) was taken in three separate standard-joint bottles

(100 ml capacity) and in each bottle 4.99 M NaCl (10 ml) and definite volume of 0.21 M NaOH (30 ml for bottle no. 1 and 2, 40 ml for bottle no. 3) were added. The H⁺ liberated on shaking reacts with NaOH and excess NaOH determined titrimetrically with 0.22 M HCl. The composition and result for each experiment are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ELUTION STUDIES

Eluent	Concn. M	Peak elution volume (V _{max}) ml	Volume for total recovery (V _i) ml	Recovery %
HCl	0.01	40	80	19.6
	0.10	50	110	32.9
	0.25	40	110	71.6
	0.50	40	100	98.2
	1.00	40	100	100.0
HNO ₃	0.10	30	80	12.0
	1.00	40	100	40.9
	2.00	40	80	46.6
	4.00	40	90	76.7
H ₂ SO ₄	0.01	40	90	10.5
	0.10	40	110	78.9
	0.25	40	90	91.5
	0.50	40	80	100.0
	1.00	30	80	100.0
HClO ₄	1.00	50	110	44.2
	2.00	40	110	73.2
	4.00	40	120	85.8
NaCl	1.00	30	70	23.9
	2.00	30	70	41.5
	4.00	30	60	62.5

TABLE 2

Amount of exchanger g	Vol of NaOH ml	Vol. of NaCl ml	Vol. of water ml	Shaking time h	Exchange capacity meq of H ⁺ /g
1.0089	30	10	10	10	2.03
1.0123	30	10	10	15	2.05
1.0175	30	10	—	20	2.08

Separation of iron from binary mixtures: Most of the elements commonly associated with iron did not interfere in its extraction which takes place at considerably lower pH (2.8). This property was utilised for the extractive separation of iron. Aqueous solutions containing iron(III) (5.1 mg) and varying amounts of foreign ions were prepared. pH of the mixture was adjusted and then passed through the column at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. Iron(III) was selectively absorbed while in most of the cases foreign ions came out with the eluent. Iron(III) from the column was eluted with 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and estimated complexometrically. The presence of nitrate, chloride or sulphate salts of metal ions (mg, amount in parenthesis) like Mn^{II}(5.0), Co^{II}(5.0), Ni^{II}(4.7), Mg^{II}(2.4), Ca^{II}(4.4), Sr^{II}(5.1), Ba^{II}(5.2), Zn^{II}(5.0), Cd^{II}(4.7), Hg^{II}(3.1), Pb^{II}(10.0), Pd^{II}(4.9), Cr^{III}(3.0), Al^{III}(2.2), Bi^{III}(10.0), La^{III}(4.8), Nd^{III}(5.1), Pr^{III}(5.1), Sm^{III}(5.1), Dy^{III}(5.9) and UO₂^{II}(5.2) did not interfere in the extraction; only Zr^{IV}(2.5) and Th^{IV}(5.2) interfered seriously.

Separation of iron from synthetic mixtures: To assess the possible analytical applications of the

proposed method, 5.1 mg of iron(III) was separated from some of the synthetic mixtures prepared by mixing each of the metal ions (~5 mg). Extractions were carried out at pH 2.8. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF Fe^{III} FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES

Fe^{III} taken = 5.1 mg, pH = 2.8, Eluant = 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Composition	Fe found mg	Fe recovery %
Co ^{II} (5.0) + Ni ^{II} (4.7)	5.1	100
Ni ^{II} (4.7) + Cu ^{II} (4.8)	5.0	98
Co ^{II} (5.0) + Cu ^{II} (4.8)	5.0	98
Cr ^{III} (4.7) + Mn ^{II} (5.0)	5.2	102
Zn ^{II} (5.0) + Cd ^{II} (5.1)	5.1	100
Al ^{III} (4.9) + Cr ^{III} (4.7)	5.0	98
La ^{III} (4.18) + Pr ^{III} (5.1)	5.0	98
Nd ^{III} (5.1) + Dy ^{III} (5.0)	5.2	102
Co ^{II} (5.0) + Ni ^{II} (4.7) + Cu ^{II} (4.8)	5.0	98
Cr ^{III} (4.7) + Co ^{II} (5.0) + Ni ^{II} (4.7)	5.1	100

Flow rate = 2 ml min⁻¹, Column = 1.5 × 7.5 cm, Silica gel coated with SRS-100 taken = 6 g.

Extraction of iron from standard ores and alloys:

To assess the possible analytical applications of the proposed method, the recommended procedure was applied for the extraction of iron in some of the standard ore and alloy samples. In most of the cases, quantitative extraction was achieved. The amount of iron(III) present in the most of the ore and alloy samples, except steel, is very low. Hence after elution iron was estimated spectrophotometrically (Table 4).

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF Fe IN ORE AND ALLOY SAMPLES

Sample	Fe recovered %	Certified Fe value %
Brass (5 g)	0.31	0.32
H. T. Brass (10 g)	1.52	1.56
Steel* (458/1)	99.46	98.72
Pyrolusite (18)	0.87	0.89
Alloy steel* (Cr V; 640)	97.52	96.82
Chrome-iron ore (49 eG)	11.32	11.60

*Estimation of Fe was done complexometrically

Process of extraction of iron from standard ores and alloys:

Brass (Sn + Cu + Pb + Fe + Zn) sample was treated with water (5 ml) and concentrated HNO₃ (10 ml) successively down the sides of the beaker and digested on a water-bath for ~1 h. When all the alloy got dissolved, it was diluted with water to a volume of 100 ml and the extraction carried out at pH 2.8. Same procedure as above was followed for H.T. brass (Cu + Fe + Sn + Pb + Zn + Al) sample. When black particles were left insoluble, the solution was filtered and washed with hot dilute HNO₃. The final volume was made to 100 ml and extracted at pH 2.8. Steel (Fe + Mn + S + P + C) sample was treated with 1 : 1 HNO₃ (20 ml) and 1 : 1 H₂SO₄ (10 ml) and heated on a water-bath

until dissolution was complete, cooled and filtered to remove carbon. The volume was then made to 100 ml and extracted at pH 2.8. Alloy steel (Cr+V+Mn+Mo+W) sample was treated with a mixture (20 ml) of H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 and H_3PO_4 (prepared by mixing 10 ml concentrated H_2SO_4 , 25 ml concentrated HNO_3 , 12.5 ml H_3PO_4 and 52.5 ml water) and boiled until dissolution was complete. Any black residue left was filtered (Whatman no. 42) and washed with the above acid mixture, cooled and diluted to 100 ml and extracted at pH 2.8.

Pyrolusite (Mn+Fe+ SiO_2) sample was dissolved in 1:1 HCl (20 ml) and evaporated to dryness on low flame and the process repeated. The mixture was then cooled, diluted, filtered, and the volume made up to 100 ml and extracted at pH 2.8. Chrome iron ore (Cr+Fe+Al+Mg); sample was fused in a 25-ml thick-walled porcelain crucible with sodium peroxide. The fused mass was transferred and the excess peroxide decomposed by heating on a water-bath. The solution was acidified with 4 M H_2SO_4

and filtered in a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark. The extraction of iron was carried out at pH 2.8.

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